

Appendix B: GCQUEST SEM analysis in JASP 0.19.3 – EduCITY

Structural Equation Modeling with 2 order FactorsModel fit

	AIC	BIC	n(Observations)	n(Parameters)		Baseline test		
				Total	Free	χ^2	df	p
Model 1			339	160	160	818.910	272.000	< .001

Note. Estimator is DWLS. Model test is scaled and shifted. Information matrix is expected. Standard errors are robust. The AIC, BIC and additional information criteria are only available with ML-type estimators.

Warnings: The variance-covariance matrix of the estimated parameters (vcov) does not appear to be positive definite! The smallest eigenvalue (= -2.114145e-16) is smaller than zero. This may be a symptom that the model is not identified.

Additional Fit Measures

Fit indices

Index	Value
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.945
Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI)	0.939
Bentler-Bonett Non-normed Fit Index (NNFI)	0.939
Bentler-Bonett Normed Fit Index (NFI)	0.920
Parsimony Normed Fit Index (PNFI)	
Bollen's Relative Fit Index (RFI)	0.911
Bollen's Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	0.945
Relative Noncentrality Index (RNI)	0.945
Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)	0.077
RMSEA 90% CI lower bound	0.071

RMSEA 90% CI upper bound	0.083
RMSEA p- value	4.037×10^{-13}
Standardized root mean square residual (SRMR)	0.049
Hoelter's critical N ($\alpha =$.05)	186.459
Hoelter's critical N ($\alpha =$.01)	197.006
Goodness of fit index (GFI)	0.992
McDonald fit index (MFI)	0.646
Expected cross validation index (ECVI)	

Note. Fit indices are based on the scaled test statistic.

	CFI	RMSEA
Estimate	0.931	0.083
Poor-fair limit	0.872	0.086
Fair- close limit	0.929	0.057

Note. T-size statistics are computed for $\alpha = 0.05$.

T-size fit indices

R Squared

	R ²
S4	0.511
S9	0.493
S10	0.365
S16	0.525
S21	0.559
S24	0.505
S2	0.488
S3	0.543
S6	0.569
S7	0.507
S8	0.562
S12	0.588
S14	0.488
S15	0.384
S18	0.555
S19	0.527
S20	0.534
S22	0.528
S23	0.555
S1	0.587
S5	0.433
S11	0.434
S13	0.535
S17	0.500
S25	0.549
Knowledge	0.997
Skills	
Attitudes	

Average variance extracted

Latent	AVE
Knowledge	0.493
Skills	0.525
Attitudes	0.506

Heterotrait-monotrait ratio

Knowledge	Skills	Attitudes
1.000		
0.999	1.000	
0.976	1.004	1.000

Parameters estimates

Factor Loadings

Latent	Indicator	Std. estimate	Std. error	z-value	p	95% Confidence interval	
						Lower	Upper
Attitudes	S1	0.766	0.021	37.256	< .001	0.726	0.806
	S5	0.658	0.028	23.696	< .001	0.603	0.712
	S11	0.659	0.024	27.146	< .001	0.612	0.707
	S13	0.732	0.020	36.052	< .001	0.692	0.771
	S17	0.707	0.022	32.373	< .001	0.664	0.750
	S25	0.741	0.025	30.197	< .001	0.693	0.789
Knowledge	S4	0.715	0.028	25.700	< .001	0.660	0.769
	S9	0.702	0.024	28.840	< .001	0.654	0.750
	S10	0.604	0.029	20.660	< .001	0.546	0.661
	S16	0.725	0.021	34.279	< .001	0.683	0.766
	S21	0.747	0.023	32.876	< .001	0.703	0.792
	S24	0.711	0.027	25.998	< .001	0.657	0.764
Skills	S2	0.699	0.028	25.373	< .001	0.645	0.752
	S3	0.737	0.022	34.164	< .001	0.695	0.779
	S6	0.754	0.021	36.165	< .001	0.713	0.795
	S7	0.712	0.027	26.021	< .001	0.658	0.766
	S8	0.750	0.023	32.346	< .001	0.704	0.795
	S12	0.767	0.020	39.071	< .001	0.729	0.806
	S14	0.699	0.023	30.329	< .001	0.654	0.744
	S15	0.619	0.026	23.631	< .001	0.568	0.671
	S18	0.745	0.022	34.424	< .001	0.702	0.787
	S19	0.726	0.023	32.109	< .001	0.682	0.770
	S20	0.731	0.024	30.438	< .001	0.684	0.778
	S22	0.726	0.025	29.120	< .001	0.677	0.775
SustainabilityValues	Knowledge	0.998	0.009	107.158	< .001	0.980	1.017
	Skills	1.005	0.006	167.331	< .001	0.993	1.016
	Attitudes	1.000	0.007	140.634	< .001	0.986	1.014

Factor variances

Variable	Std. estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence interval	
					Lower	Upper
Knowledge	0.003	0.019	0.171	0.864	-0.033	0.040
Skills	-0.009	0.012	-0.773	0.440	-0.033	0.014
Attitudes	-6.770×10^{-4}	0.014	-0.048	0.962	-0.029	0.027
SustainabilityValues	1.000	0.000			1.000	1.000

Residual variances

Variable	Std. estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence interval	
					Lower	Upper
S4	0.489	0.040	12.303	< .001	0.411	0.567
S9	0.507	0.034	14.829	< .001	0.440	0.574
S10	0.635	0.035	18.009	< .001	0.566	0.705
S16	0.475	0.031	15.492	< .001	0.415	0.535
S21	0.441	0.034	12.987	< .001	0.375	0.508
S24	0.495	0.039	12.725	< .001	0.418	0.571
S2	0.512	0.038	13.315	< .001	0.437	0.587
S3	0.457	0.032	14.355	< .001	0.394	0.519
S6	0.431	0.031	13.703	< .001	0.369	0.493
S7	0.493	0.039	12.652	< .001	0.417	0.569
S8	0.438	0.035	12.594	< .001	0.370	0.506
S12	0.412	0.030	13.660	< .001	0.352	0.471
S14	0.512	0.032	15.886	< .001	0.448	0.575
S15	0.616	0.032	18.977	< .001	0.553	0.680
S18	0.445	0.032	13.814	< .001	0.382	0.508
S19	0.473	0.033	14.411	< .001	0.409	0.537
S20	0.466	0.035	13.286	< .001	0.397	0.535
S22	0.472	0.036	13.037	< .001	0.401	0.543
S23	0.445	0.032	13.920	< .001	0.382	0.507
S1	0.413	0.031	13.122	< .001	0.352	0.475
S5	0.567	0.037	15.544	< .001	0.496	0.639
S11	0.566	0.032	17.667	< .001	0.503	0.628
S13	0.465	0.030	15.645	< .001	0.406	0.523
S17	0.500	0.031	16.185	< .001	0.439	0.561
S25	0.451	0.036	12.409	< .001	0.380	0.522

Intercepts

Variable	Std. estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence interval	
					Lower	Upper
S4	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S9	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S10	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S16	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S21	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S24	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S2	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S3	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S6	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S7	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S8	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S12	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S14	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S15	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S18	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S19	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S20	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S22	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S23	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S1	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S5	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S11	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S13	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S17	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
S25	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
Knowledge	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
Skills	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
Attitudes	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000
SustainabilityValues	0.000	0.000			0.000	0.000

Thresholds

Variable	Threshold	Std. estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence interval	
						Lower	Upper
S4	t1	-2.518	0.249	-10.126	< .001	-3.005	-2.031
	t2	-1.846	0.133	-13.906	< .001	-2.106	-1.586
	t3	-1.047	0.084	-12.518	< .001	-1.211	-0.883
	t4	-0.304	0.069	-4.386	< .001	-0.440	-0.168
	t5	0.513	0.072	7.177	< .001	0.373	0.654
S9	t1	-2.372	0.213	-11.151	< .001	-2.789	-1.955
	t2	-2.104	0.164	-12.800	< .001	-2.426	-1.782
	t3	-0.700	0.075	-9.386	< .001	-0.846	-0.554
	t4	-0.107	0.068	-1.572	0.116	-0.241	0.026
	t5	0.748	0.076	9.900	< .001	0.600	0.896
S10	t1	-2.041	0.155	-13.123	< .001	-2.345	-1.736
	t2	-1.332	0.095	-13.960	< .001	-1.519	-1.145
	t3	-0.565	0.072	-7.814	< .001	-0.706	-0.423
	t4	0.220	0.069	3.197	0.001	0.085	0.355
	t5	0.872	0.078	11.107	< .001	0.718	1.025
S16	t1	-2.518	0.249	-10.126	< .001	-3.005	-2.031
	t2	-1.888	0.137	-13.766	< .001	-2.157	-1.619
	t3	-1.170	0.088	-13.273	< .001	-1.343	-0.997
	t4	-0.488	0.071	-6.857	< .001	-0.628	-0.349
	t5	0.480	0.071	6.750	< .001	0.341	0.619
	t6	2.753	0.327	8.411	< .001	2.112	3.395
S21	t1	-2.264	0.191	-11.863	< .001	-2.638	-1.890
	t2	-2.177	0.176	-12.391	< .001	-2.521	-1.832
	t3	-0.973	0.081	-11.971	< .001	-1.133	-0.814
	t4	-0.235	0.069	-3.414	< .001	-0.370	-0.100
	t5	0.829	0.077	10.710	< .001	0.677	0.981
S24	t1	-2.041	0.155	-13.123	< .001	-2.345	-1.736
	t2	-1.736	0.122	-14.184	< .001	-1.976	-1.496
	t3	-1.060	0.084	-12.606	< .001	-1.225	-0.895
	t4	-0.175	0.069	-2.548	0.011	-0.309	-0.040
	t5	0.882	0.079	11.205	< .001	0.728	1.037

S2	t1	-2.264	0.191	-11.863	< .001	-2.638	-1.890
	t2	-1.673	0.117	-14.282	< .001	-1.902	-1.443
	t3	-1.047	0.084	-12.518	< .001	-1.211	-0.883
	t4	0.063	0.068	0.922	0.357	-0.071	0.197
	t5	0.904	0.079	11.399	< .001	0.749	1.060
S3	t1	-2.518	0.249	-10.126	< .001	-3.005	-2.031
	t2	-2.264	0.191	-11.863	< .001	-2.638	-1.890
	t3	-1.010	0.082	-12.248	< .001	-1.171	-0.848
	t4	-0.227	0.069	-3.305	< .001	-0.362	-0.093
	t5	0.758	0.076	10.003	< .001	0.610	0.907
S6	t1	-2.372	0.213	-11.151	< .001	-2.789	-1.955
	t2	-1.807	0.129	-14.020	< .001	-2.059	-1.554
	t3	-1.247	0.091	-13.642	< .001	-1.426	-1.068
	t4	-0.289	0.069	-4.170	< .001	-0.424	-0.153
	t5	0.407	0.070	5.786	< .001	0.269	0.544
S7	t1	-2.264	0.191	-11.863	< .001	-2.638	-1.890
	t2	-1.934	0.142	-13.594	< .001	-2.213	-1.655
	t3	-1.332	0.095	-13.960	< .001	-1.519	-1.145
	t4	-0.439	0.071	-6.215	< .001	-0.577	-0.300
	t5	0.565	0.072	7.814	< .001	0.423	0.706
S8	t1	-2.518	0.249	-10.126	< .001	-3.005	-2.031
	t2	-1.934	0.142	-13.594	< .001	-2.213	-1.655
	t3	-0.997	0.082	-12.156	< .001	-1.158	-0.837
	t4	-0.243	0.069	-3.522	< .001	-0.378	-0.108
	t5	0.681	0.074	9.178	< .001	0.536	0.827
S12	t1	-2.264	0.191	-11.863	< .001	-2.638	-1.890
	t2	-1.934	0.142	-13.594	< .001	-2.213	-1.655
	t3	-0.985	0.082	-12.064	< .001	-1.145	-0.825
	t4	-0.327	0.070	-4.710	< .001	-0.464	-0.191
	t5	0.788	0.076	10.308	< .001	0.638	0.938
	t6	2.753	0.327	8.411	< .001	2.112	3.395

S14	t1	-2.264	0.191	-11.863	< .001	-2.638	-1.890
	t2	-1.985	0.148	-13.383	< .001	-2.275	-1.694
	t3	-0.950	0.081	-11.783	< .001	-1.108	-0.792
	t4	-0.447	0.071	-6.322	< .001	-0.586	-0.308
	t5	0.447	0.071	6.322	< .001	0.308	0.586
	t6	2.753	0.327	8.411	< .001	2.112	3.395
S15	t1	-2.177	0.176	-12.391	< .001	-2.521	-1.832
	t2	-1.807	0.129	-14.020	< .001	-2.059	-1.554
	t3	-0.997	0.082	-12.156	< .001	-1.158	-0.837
	t4	-0.383	0.070	-5.464	< .001	-0.520	-0.245
	t5	0.375	0.070	5.356	< .001	0.238	0.512
	t6	2.753	0.327	8.411	< .001	2.112	3.395
S18	t1	-2.104	0.164	-12.800	< .001	-2.426	-1.782
	t2	-1.703	0.120	-14.240	< .001	-1.938	-1.469
	t3	-1.200	0.089	-13.426	< .001	-1.375	-1.025
	t4	-0.182	0.069	-2.656	0.008	-0.317	-0.048
	t5	0.407	0.070	5.786	< .001	0.269	0.544
S19	t1	-2.372	0.213	-11.151	< .001	-2.789	-1.955
	t2	-1.770	0.125	-14.111	< .001	-2.016	-1.524
	t3	-0.962	0.081	-11.877	< .001	-1.120	-0.803
	t4	-0.078	0.068	-1.139	0.255	-0.211	0.056
	t5	0.768	0.076	10.105	< .001	0.619	0.917
S20	t1	-2.753	0.327	-8.411	< .001	-3.395	-2.112
	t2	-1.934	0.142	-13.594	< .001	-2.213	-1.655
	t3	-1.448	0.102	-14.238	< .001	-1.648	-1.249
	t4	-0.367	0.070	-5.248	< .001	-0.504	-0.230
	t5	0.463	0.071	6.536	< .001	0.324	0.602
S22	t1	-2.518	0.249	-10.126	< .001	-3.005	-2.031
	t2	-1.985	0.148	-13.383	< .001	-2.275	-1.694
	t3	-1.170	0.088	-13.273	< .001	-1.343	-0.997
	t4	-0.078	0.068	-1.139	0.255	-0.211	0.056
	t5	0.719	0.075	9.592	< .001	0.572	0.866
S23	t1	-2.177	0.176	-12.391	< .001	-2.521	-1.832
	t2	-1.807	0.129	-14.020	< .001	-2.059	-1.554
	t3	-1.185	0.089	-13.350	< .001	-1.359	-1.011
	t4	-0.281	0.069	-4.062	< .001	-0.416	-0.145

S1	t5	0.872	0.078	11.107	< .001	0.718	1.025
	t1	-2.177	0.176	-12.391	< .001	-2.521	-1.832
	t2	-1.934	0.142	-13.594	< .001	-2.213	-1.655
	t3	-1.060	0.084	-12.606	< .001	-1.225	-0.895
	t4	-0.312	0.069	-4.494	< .001	-0.448	-0.176
S5	t5	0.739	0.075	9.798	< .001	0.591	0.886
	t1	-2.518	0.249	-10.126	< .001	-3.005	-2.031
	t2	-1.888	0.137	-13.766	< .001	-2.157	-1.619
	t3	-1.369	0.097	-14.067	< .001	-1.559	-1.178
	t4	-0.547	0.072	-7.602	< .001	-0.689	-0.406
S11	t5	0.250	0.069	3.630	< .001	0.115	0.385
	t1	-2.518	0.249	-10.126	< .001	-3.005	-2.031
	t2	-1.934	0.142	-13.594	< .001	-2.213	-1.655
	t3	-1.060	0.084	-12.606	< .001	-1.225	-0.895
	t4	-0.197	0.069	-2.873	0.004	-0.332	-0.063
	t5	0.513	0.072	7.177	< .001	0.373	0.654
S13	t6	2.753	0.327	8.411	< .001	2.112	3.395
	t1	-1.985	0.148	-13.383	< .001	-2.275	-1.694
	t2	-1.807	0.129	-14.020	< .001	-2.059	-1.554
	t3	-1.127	0.087	-13.032	< .001	-1.297	-0.958
	t4	-0.375	0.070	-5.356	< .001	-0.512	-0.238
	t5	0.719	0.075	9.592	< .001	0.572	0.866
S17	t6	2.753	0.327	8.411	< .001	2.112	3.395
	t1	-2.264	0.191	-11.863	< .001	-2.638	-1.890
	t2	-1.846	0.133	-13.906	< .001	-2.106	-1.586
	t3	-1.215	0.090	-13.500	< .001	-1.392	-1.039
	t4	-0.539	0.072	-7.496	< .001	-0.680	-0.398
	t5	0.415	0.070	5.893	< .001	0.277	0.552
S25	t6	2.753	0.327	8.411	< .001	2.112	3.395
	t1	-2.177	0.176	-12.391	< .001	-2.521	-1.832
	t2	-1.934	0.142	-13.594	< .001	-2.213	-1.655
	t3	-1.215	0.090	-13.500	< .001	-1.392	-1.039
	t4	-0.480	0.071	-6.750	< .001	-0.619	-0.341
	t5	0.547	0.072	7.602	< .001	0.406	0.689

Covariance tables

Observed covariance matrix

S4	S9	S10	S16	S21	S24	S2	S3	S6	S7	S8	S12	S14	S15	S18	S19
1.000															
0.487	1.000														
0.375	0.447	1.000													
0.509	0.509	0.497	1.000												
0.515	0.530	0.442	0.537	1.000											
0.470	0.540	0.442	0.481	0.556	1.000										
0.505	0.460	0.470	0.509	0.489	0.477	1.000									
0.620	0.526	0.484	0.513	0.565	0.538	0.562	1.000								
0.566	0.591	0.593	0.553	0.489	0.435	0.536	0.515	1.000							
0.554	0.486	0.433	0.498	0.506	0.503	0.556	0.500	0.611	1.000						
0.488	0.631	0.489	0.551	0.581	0.475	0.511	0.523	0.619	0.588	1.000					
0.587	0.491	0.454	0.574	0.561	0.506	0.544	0.542	0.577	0.508	0.529	1.000				
0.486	0.415	0.335	0.491	0.548	0.502	0.312	0.497	0.452	0.436	0.477	0.551	1.000			
0.413	0.308	0.376	0.570	0.431	0.413	0.393	0.427	0.422	0.360	0.418	0.516	0.569	1.000		
0.480	0.434	0.472	0.548	0.586	0.509	0.431	0.545	0.610	0.582	0.566	0.531	0.525	0.471	1.000	
0.515	0.549	0.402	0.542	0.511	0.524	0.498	0.507	0.544	0.529	0.542	0.524	0.528	0.433	0.587	1.000
0.565	0.508	0.390	0.565	0.592	0.532	0.549	0.568	0.554	0.452	0.540	0.609	0.481	0.366	0.513	0.572
0.465	0.592	0.480	0.443	0.587	0.459	0.473	0.573	0.530	0.500	0.620	0.529	0.537	0.465	0.531	0.465
0.484	0.547	0.472	0.501	0.568	0.497	0.500	0.527	0.584	0.550	0.652	0.562	0.454	0.482	0.586	0.579
0.582	0.580	0.477	0.524	0.573	0.564	0.684	0.619	0.565	0.577	0.513	0.589	0.476	0.381	0.575	0.576
0.540	0.394	0.323	0.433	0.422	0.468	0.432	0.538	0.554	0.483	0.455	0.442	0.467	0.458	0.550	0.515
0.415	0.418	0.289	0.496	0.477	0.452	0.430	0.466	0.454	0.409	0.418	0.626	0.565	0.514	0.531	0.448
0.500	0.457	0.389	0.532	0.518	0.563	0.505	0.529	0.489	0.495	0.485	0.639	0.662	0.510	0.472	0.522
0.504	0.458	0.328	0.601	0.527	0.595	0.387	0.441	0.445	0.478	0.518	0.614	0.594	0.537	0.582	0.514
0.526	0.561	0.430	0.483	0.629	0.594	0.531	0.527	0.565	0.587	0.512	0.547	0.507	0.383	0.474	0.528

Implied covariance matrix

S4	S9	S10	S16	S21	S24	S2	S3	S6	S7	S8	S12	S14	S15	S18	S19
1.000															
0.502	1.000														
0.432	0.424	1.000													
0.518	0.509	0.438	1.000												
0.534	0.525	0.451	0.542	1.000											
0.508	0.499	0.429	0.515	0.531	1.000										
0.501	0.492	0.423	0.508	0.524	0.498	1.000									
0.528	0.519	0.446	0.536	0.553	0.526	0.515	1.000								
0.541	0.531	0.457	0.548	0.565	0.538	0.527	0.556	1.000							
0.510	0.501	0.431	0.518	0.534	0.508	0.497	0.525	0.537	1.000						
0.538	0.528	0.454	0.545	0.562	0.535	0.524	0.553	0.566	0.534	1.000					
0.550	0.540	0.465	0.558	0.575	0.547	0.536	0.565	0.579	0.546	0.575	1.000				
0.501	0.492	0.423	0.508	0.524	0.498	0.488	0.515	0.527	0.498	0.524	0.536	1.000			
0.444	0.436	0.375	0.450	0.464	0.442	0.433	0.457	0.467	0.441	0.464	0.475	0.433	1.000		
0.534	0.525	0.451	0.541	0.558	0.531	0.520	0.549	0.562	0.530	0.558	0.571	0.521	0.461	1.000	
0.520	0.511	0.440	0.528	0.544	0.518	0.507	0.535	0.548	0.517	0.544	0.557	0.507	0.450	0.541	1.000
0.524	0.515	0.443	0.531	0.548	0.521	0.510	0.539	0.551	0.520	0.548	0.561	0.511	0.453	0.544	0.530
0.521	0.512	0.440	0.528	0.545	0.518	0.507	0.535	0.548	0.517	0.545	0.557	0.508	0.450	0.541	0.527
0.534	0.525	0.451	0.542	0.559	0.531	0.521	0.549	0.562	0.531	0.559	0.572	0.521	0.462	0.555	0.541
0.547	0.537	0.462	0.554	0.572	0.544	0.538	0.567	0.581	0.548	0.577	0.591	0.538	0.477	0.573	0.559
0.469	0.461	0.397	0.476	0.491	0.467	0.462	0.487	0.499	0.471	0.496	0.507	0.462	0.409	0.492	0.480
0.471	0.462	0.397	0.477	0.492	0.468	0.463	0.488	0.500	0.472	0.497	0.508	0.463	0.410	0.493	0.481
0.522	0.513	0.441	0.530	0.546	0.519	0.514	0.542	0.555	0.524	0.551	0.564	0.514	0.455	0.548	0.534
0.505	0.496	0.426	0.512	0.528	0.502	0.496	0.524	0.536	0.506	0.533	0.545	0.497	0.440	0.529	0.516
0.529	0.520	0.447	0.536	0.553	0.526	0.520	0.549	0.562	0.530	0.558	0.571	0.520	0.461	0.555	0.541

Residuals covariance matrix

S4	S9	S10	S16	S21	S24	S2	S3	S6	S7	S8	S12	S14	S15	S18
0.000														
-0.015	0.000													
-0.056	0.023	0.000												
-0.009	3.366x10 ⁻⁴	0.059	0.000											
-0.020	0.005	-0.010	-0.005	0.000										
-0.038	0.041	0.013	-0.034	0.024	0.000									
0.004	-0.032	0.047	0.001	-0.035	-0.021	0.000								
0.091	0.007	0.038	-0.022	0.012	0.013	0.047	0.000							
0.026	0.060	0.136	0.004	-0.077	-0.103	0.009	-0.041	0.000						
0.043	-0.016	0.001	-0.020	-0.028	-0.004	0.059	-0.025	0.074	0.000					
-0.049	0.103	0.035	0.006	0.019	-0.059	-0.012	-0.029	0.054	0.054	0.000				
0.037	-0.049	-0.011	0.016	-0.014	-0.041	0.008	-0.023	-0.001	-0.039	-0.046	0.000			
-0.015	-0.077	-0.088	-0.017	0.024	0.003	-0.176	-0.018	-0.075	-0.061	-0.047	0.015	0.000		
-0.031	-0.128	7.458x10 ⁻⁴	0.120	-0.033	-0.029	-0.039	-0.030	-0.045	-0.082	-0.046	0.041	0.137	0.000	
-0.054	-0.091	0.021	0.007	0.028	-0.022	-0.089	-0.004	0.048	0.051	0.007	-0.040	0.005	0.010	0.000
-0.005	0.038	-0.038	0.015	-0.033	0.006	-0.009	-0.028	-0.004	0.012	-0.002	-0.032	0.020	-0.016	0.047
0.041	-0.007	-0.052	0.034	0.045	0.011	0.039	0.029	0.003	-0.068	-0.008	0.049	-0.029	-0.087	-0.031
-0.056	0.080	0.040	-0.085	0.043	-0.059	-0.034	0.037	-0.018	-0.017	0.075	-0.028	0.030	0.015	-0.010
-0.050	0.022	0.021	-0.040	0.009	-0.034	-0.020	-0.022	0.022	0.019	0.093	-0.010	-0.067	0.020	0.031
0.036	0.043	0.015	-0.030	0.001	0.020	0.146	0.052	-0.015	0.029	-0.064	-0.002	-0.062	-0.096	0.001
0.070	-0.067	-0.074	-0.043	-0.069	0.001	-0.030	0.051	0.056	0.013	-0.041	-0.065	0.005	0.048	0.057
-0.055	-0.045	-0.109	0.019	-0.015	-0.016	-0.033	-0.022	-0.046	-0.062	-0.078	0.118	0.102	0.104	0.037
-0.022	-0.056	-0.052	0.002	-0.029	0.043	-0.008	-0.013	-0.066	-0.028	-0.066	0.075	0.148	0.054	-0.076
-7.241x10 ⁻⁴	-0.038	-0.099	0.089	-8.222x10 ⁻⁴	0.093	-0.110	-0.083	-0.091	-0.028	-0.015	0.069	0.098	0.097	0.053
-0.003	0.041	-0.017	-0.053	0.076	0.068	0.011	-0.022	0.003	0.057	-0.047	-0.024	-0.013	-0.078	-0.081

Standardized residuals covariance matrix

S4	S9	S10	S16	S21	S24	S2	S3	S6	S7	S8	S12	S14	S15	S18	S19
0.000															
-0.668	0.000														
-1.854	0.773	0.000													
-0.438	0.016	2.585	0.000												
-0.785	0.239	-0.336	-0.253	0.000											
-1.866	1.527	0.434	-1.800	1.226	0.000										
0.164	-1.311	1.797	0.045	-1.488	-0.770	0.000									
4.319	0.252	1.254	-1.202	0.488	0.557	2.018	0.000								
1.121	2.329	5.008	0.229	-3.472	-3.812	0.378	-1.444	0.000							
1.710	-0.592	0.044	-0.945	-1.137	-0.216	2.138	-0.936	2.847	0.000						
-2.519	4.433	1.262	0.341	0.709	-2.743	-0.641	-1.157	2.610	2.447	0.000					
1.787	-2.437	-0.509	0.639	-0.804	-2.121	0.405	-1.514	-0.061	-2.003	-2.672	0.000				
-0.687	-3.056	-2.948	-0.600	0.988	0.162	-6.394	-0.850	-2.773	-2.676	-1.877	0.565	0.000			
-1.247	-4.641	0.024	4.321	-1.344	-1.161	-1.259	-1.373	-1.563	-2.641	-1.755	1.595	4.907	0.000		
-2.138	-3.109	0.687	0.386	1.184	-0.955	-3.258	-0.144	1.827	2.029	0.301	-2.483	0.222	0.452	0.000	
-0.219	1.372	-1.474	0.858	-1.288	0.311	-0.385	-1.132	-0.123	0.514	-0.095	-1.773	0.895	-0.703	2.131	0.000
1.801	-0.212	-1.789	1.701	1.699	0.377	1.430	1.267	0.114	-2.964	-0.343	2.322	-1.310	-3.176	-1.202	1.697
-2.227	3.289	1.498	-3.579	2.097	-2.655	-1.487	1.571	-0.657	-0.581	4.225	-1.455	1.257	0.505	-0.362	-2.933
-1.991	0.777	0.759	-2.229	0.414	-1.607	-0.874	-0.800	0.818	0.786	4.464	-0.620	-3.135	0.926	1.349	1.517
1.590	1.844	0.600	-1.702	0.069	0.996	6.788	1.819	-0.617	1.194	-3.515	-0.119	-2.946	-4.347	0.055	0.611
2.582	-2.143	-2.382	-1.821	-2.703	0.050	-1.086	1.688	1.920	0.432	-1.560	-3.093	0.193	1.706	2.054	1.276
-2.353	-1.906	-3.644	0.631	-0.612	-0.747	-1.250	-1.124	-1.627	-2.198	-2.900	4.735	3.919	3.633	1.760	-1.469
-1.052	-2.239	-2.194	0.089	-1.387	2.576	-0.375	-0.712	-2.863	-1.393	-3.370	3.473	5.599	2.092	-3.949	-0.570
-0.035	-1.498	-3.689	3.510	-0.043	5.156	-3.804	-3.815	-3.899	-1.311	-0.556	2.694	3.351	3.721	2.996	-0.119
-0.112	1.702	-0.588	-2.607	3.782	3.363	0.462	-1.004	0.131	2.501	-2.323	-1.387	-0.613	-2.947	-3.290	-0.486

Path diagram

